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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Immunotherapies have revolutionized cancer treatment, and immune checkpoint inhibitors are now widely utilized in the management of various malignancies. However, immune-related adverse events associated with immunotherapy are increasingly recognized. Among endocrine toxicities, thyroid dysfunction—particularly hypothyroidism—is one of the most frequently observed adverse effects. In this study, we present a case of hypothyroidism that developed following nivolumab treatment and discuss its management approach.

Case Presentation: A 62-year-old male patient was under follow-up for non-small cell lung cancer (adenocarcinoma). Following disease progression after first-line treatment with pemetrexed and cisplatin, nivolumab was initiated as second-line therapy. After six cycles, the patient developed prominent symptoms of hypothyroidism, including fatigue, somnolence, and constipation. Laboratory tests revealed a markedly elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) level (82 mIU/L, normal: 0.4–4.0 mIU/L) and decreased levels of free triiodothyronine (fT3: 1.5 pg/mL, normal: 2.0–4.4 pg/mL) and free thyroxine (fT4: 0.5 ng/dL, normal: 0.9–1.7 ng/dL). Both thyroid peroxidase antibody (anti-TPO) and thyroglobulin antibody (anti-TG) were negative. Thyroid ultrasonography revealed a hypoechoic and heterogeneous parenchymal structure. These findings were consistent with immune-related hypothyroidism.

Discussion: Nivolumab treatment was temporarily withheld, and levothyroxine replacement therapy was initiated at a dose of 100 mcg/day based on clinical severity and patient weight. Within a week, clinical improvement was observed, and thyroid function tests showed recovery. Notably, nivolumab therapy was successfully resumed without the need for permanent discontinuation, allowing continued cancer treatment. Within six weeks, the patient's thyroid function tests stabilized with minimal adjustments to the levothyroxine dose (TSH: 9 mIU/L, fT3: 3 pg/mL, fT4: 1.6 ng/dL), and immunotherapy was safely continued. The patient remains under multidisciplinary follow-up in both endocrinology and oncology outpatient clinics.

Conclusion: Hypothyroidism induced by immunotherapy can be effectively managed without discontinuing treatment if diagnosed early and appropriately treated. Therefore, regular monitoring of thyroid function tests is essential in patients receiving immunotherapy, and early replacement therapy should be initiated in symptomatic cases. This case highlights the importance of early recognition and multidisciplinary management of immune-related hypothyroidism in patients undergoing checkpoint inhibitor therapy.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Immunotherapy, hypothyroidism, nivolumab, immune-related adverse events

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, immunotherapies have emerged as an effective treatment option for various types of cancer, including metastatic lung cancer (Pardoll, 2012). Immune checkpoint inhibitors activate the immune system against cancer cells, providing a significant therapeutic option (Topalian, Drake, & Pardoll, 2015). Specifically, inhibitors targeting Programmed Cell Death Protein 1 (PD-1) / Programmed Cell Death Ligand

1 (PD-L1) and Cytotoxic T-Lymphocyte-Associated Protein 4 (CTLA-4) have been widely incorporated into the treatment of multiple solid tumors (Barroso-Sousa et al., 2018).

However, these therapies target not only tumor cells but also lead to various immune-related adverse events due to excessive immune system activation (Postow, Sidlow, & Hellmann, 2018). These adverse effects can involve the dermatologic, gastrointestinal, pulmonary, and endocrine systems (Naidoo et al., 2015). Among the most commonly observed endocrine side effects are hypophysitis, adrenal insufficiency, and thyroid dysfunction (Abdel-Rahman, ElHalawani, & Fouad, 2016). Immunotherapy-induced hypothyroidism may present as either subclinical or overt hypothyroidism and, in most cases, becomes permanent, requiring lifelong replacement therapy (Postow et al., 2018).

In this report, we present a case of hypothyroidism following nivolumab therapy and discuss its diagnosis and the management of immune-related endocrine adverse effects.

CASE PRESENTATION

This case report was conducted in accordance with ethical principles and institutional guidelines. The patient was followed at the Medical Oncology Department of Ordu University Training and Research Hospital. Clinical follow-up, biochemical evaluations, and imaging procedures were performed during the course of nivolumab therapy as part of routine clinical care.

Thyroid function was assessed at baseline and monitored regularly throughout the treatment period, including measurements of serum TSH, free T4, and anti-thyroid antibodies. When the patient presented with symptoms suggestive of thyroid dysfunction, thyroid ultrasonography and repeat laboratory evaluations were performed. A diagnosis of immune-related hypothyroidism was established based on clinical presentation and laboratory findings. Levothyroxine replacement therapy was initiated under the guidance of the endocrinology department. Immunotherapy was temporarily withheld and later resumed after stabilization of thyroid function.

Data collection was limited to routine clinical assessments, and no experimental procedures were performed. Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case. Ethics committee approval was not required for this case report.

A 62-year-old male patient with a history of hypertension but no other known chronic diseases had a 40 pack-year smoking history and was still smoking. There was no family history of malignancy or endocrine disorders. In March 2023, the patient presented to the pulmonology outpatient clinic with complaints of cough and hemoptysis. Thoracic computed tomography (CT) revealed a 7.5 cm primary mass in the lower lobe of the left lung, along with mediastinal lymphadenopathy. Histopathological evaluation of the bronchoscopic biopsy confirmed the diagnosis of non-small cell lung cancer (adenocarcinoma).

A positron emission tomography/computed tomography (PET/CT) scan performed to assess disease extent identified a 7 cm primary mass in the lower lobe of the left lung with a maximum standardized uptake value (SUVmax) of 16.5, exceeding the commonly accepted malignancy threshold and strongly suggesting a neoplastic process. Increased metabolic activity was observed in the mediastinal lymph nodes, with the highest SUVmax reaching 9. Multiple bone metastases were detected, with a maximum SUVmax reaching 11 in these lesions. Genetic analysis revealed no mutations suitable for targeted therapy, and PD-L1 expression was reported as weakly positive (1–49%).

First-line treatment with pemetrexed plus cisplatin was initiated. After three cycles, a partial response was observed, leading to the continuation of treatment for an additional three cycles. However, after the sixth cycle, PET-CT imaging revealed disease progression, including new bone metastases and bilateral metastatic lung lesions. Consequently, nivolumab was initiated as second-line therapy.

After approximately three months of treatment, a significant regression of both the primary tumor and metastatic lesions was observed. However, after three months of nivolumab therapy, the patient developed severe fatigue, persistent somnolence, and constipation. On physical examination, the patient was in good general condition, cooperative, and oriented. The skin and mucous membranes appeared pale, with no evidence of significant peripheral edema or dehydration. Vital signs were as follows: blood pressure, 125/90 mmHg; pulse rate, 62 bpm; respiratory rate, 18 breaths per minute; and body temperature, 36.8°C. Cardiovascular examination revealed no abnormal heart sounds or murmurs. Pulmonary auscultation revealed decreased breath sounds in the left lower lobe and basal inspiratory rales. No pathological findings were observed on gastrointestinal examination, and neurological examination revealed no motor or sensory deficits, although the patient reported marked fatigue and difficulty concentrating.

Laboratory tests revealed a hemoglobin level of 11.2 g/dL, a leukocyte count of 7,800/mm³, and a platelet count of 250,000/mm³. Renal function tests were within normal limits, with a creatinine level of 0.9 mg/dL. Liver function tests showed alanine aminotransferase (ALT) at 24 U/L, aspartate aminotransferase (AST) at 28 U/L, total bilirubin at 1.1 mg/dL, direct bilirubin at 0.4 mg/dL, alkaline phosphatase (ALP) at 213 U/L, and gamma-glutamyl transferase (GGT) at 55 U/L. C-reactive protein (CRP) was 7.2 mg/L, lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) was 289 U/L, and albumin was 3.8 g/dL. Electrolyte levels were as follows: sodium, 138 mmol/L; potassium, 4 mmol/L; calcium, 8.8 mg/dL; and magnesium, 0.88 mmol/L.

Endocrine evaluation revealed a markedly elevated thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) level (82 mIU/L, normal: 0.4–4.0 mIU/L), along with low free triiodothyronine (fT3: 1.5 pg/mL, normal: 2.0–4.4 pg/mL) and free thyroxine (fT4: 0.5 ng/dL, normal: 0.9–1.7 ng/dL) levels. Additional pituitary hormone tests were performed to assess for hypophysitis-related panhypopituitarism, but no abnormalities were detected other than the elevated TSH level. The patient had normal thyroid function tests prior to initiating nivolumab. To investigate the etiology of hypothyroidism, anti-thyroid peroxidase (anti-TPO) and anti-thyroglobulin (anti-TG) antibodies were tested and found negative. Thyroid ultrasonography revealed diffuse heterogeneity, a mild reduction in gland size, and decreased parenchymal echogenicity, consistent with hypothyroidism. No nodules or significant inflammatory changes were detected.

Given the significant thyroid function abnormalities, the patient was referred to the endocrinology department, where a diagnosis of immunotherapy-induced hypothyroidism was confirmed. Nivolumab therapy was temporarily withheld, and levothyroxine replacement therapy was initiated at a dose of 100 mcg/day based on clinical severity and patient weight. Follow-up testing after one week showed normalization of fT4 levels (1.2 ng/dL) and near-normalization of fT3 levels (1.9 pg/mL), accompanied by significant improvement in the patient's symptoms. At the two-week follow-up, the patient's somnolence and dizziness had resolved, and constipation showed improvement. Consequently, nivolumab therapy was resumed, and levothyroxine treatment was maintained.

Six weeks later, follow-up laboratory results showed a mildly elevated TSH level (9 mIU/L), while fT3 (3 pg/mL) and fT4 (1.6 ng/dL) remained within normal ranges. The levothyroxine dose was adjusted accordingly to maintain optimal thyroid function. Based on these findings, the patient was scheduled for regular followup in the endocrinology outpatient clinic, and nivolumab therapy was continued.

DISCUSSION

Although immunotherapies have revolutionized cancer treatment, they may also cause immune-related adverse events (Gonzalez-Rodriguez & Rodriguez-Abreu, 2016). Among these adverse effects, endocrine dysfunctions, particularly thyroid disorders, are among the most frequently observed (Muir et al., 2021). Thyroid disorders associated with immunotherapy typically manifest as hypothyroidism, thyroiditis, or hyperthyroidism. Clinically, both subclinical and overt hypothyroidism can develop, with most cases requiring thyroid hormone replacement therapy (Brahmer et al., 2018). This phenomenon is attributed to both the direct and indirect immune effects of immune checkpoint inhibitors on the thyroid gland. The absence of anti-TPO and anti-TG antibodies supports the diagnosis of destructive thyroiditis secondary to immunotherapy rather than classic autoimmune thyroid disease.

In this case study, the early diagnosis and appropriate management of hypothyroidism following nivolumab therapy were comprehensively evaluated. The patient's clinical symptoms, changes in thyroid function tests, and ultrasound findings, indicated immune-related thyroid dysfunction. Studies have shown that thyroid function abnormalities occur in approximately 10–20% of patients undergoing immunotherapy (Morganstein et al., 2017). Therefore, thyroid function tests should be regularly monitored at baseline and throughout the treatment course in patients receiving immunotherapy. This approach facilitates the early detection of immune-related endocrinopathies and allows for the timely implementation of appropriate treatment strategies.

In conclusion, early detection and appropriate management are crucial for minimizing the impact of immune-related thyroid dysfunction during immunotherapy. In our case, hypothyroidism that developed following nivolumab therapy was effectively managed with appropriate replacement therapy. Notably, immunotherapy was resumed without the need for permanent discontinuation, demonstrating that endocrine immune-related adverse events can be effectively managed without disrupting oncologic treatment. A multidisciplinary approach was implemented throughout this process.

A better understanding and management of endocrine adverse effects related to immunotherapy will aid in the early diagnosis and treatment of potential complications, ultimately enhancing patient prognosis and quality of life. Although immune checkpoint inhibitors have significantly advanced malignancy treatment, immune-related endocrine adverse effects can complicate patient management. Therefore, close endocrinological monitoring of patients receiving immunotherapy is crucial, particularly during the first few months of treatment and in the long term, as immune-related endocrine dysfunctions may manifest even after therapy discontinuation.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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